

Knowledge graph implementation and contextual, graph-based learning path recommendation roadmap for our personalized learning environment

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Introduction

Knowledge graphs are semantic knowledge modeling and representation tools, composed of entities and relations amongst those entities. Their ability to represent the semantic relation between entities enables them to provide information of the context, in which a graph entity may exist. This contextual information is used to support a decision support algorithm, that is based on the knowledge modeled in the knowledge graph.

In the scope of OSCAR's personalized learning environment (eDoer), student decisions about their learning paths are supported with a recommender system. The recommendation provides the user with suggestions about topics and learning materials to study, in order to gain skills that enable them to perform a corresponding job.

The eDoer platform is designed to feature two recommendation systems, working in harmony to provide the user with the best recommendation in each learning scenario:

- Expert-rule-based recommender system, which generated recommendations to the user based on hand-crafted rules and intelligent models that are trained on those rules.
- Graph-based recommender system, which generates the recommendations based on the semantic relations between graph entities, with the potential to additionally integrate rules.

The knowledge graph based recommender system is designed to utilize the collected data about users, jobs, skills, topics, and OERs, in which the eDoer platform is organized into, in order to predict the relations between a certain user and the skills, topics or OERs that enables them to reach their pre-defined learning goals best. Figure 1 shows the integration concept of the graph recommender system with the eDoer platform. The focus on the graph not only enables contextualized decisions, but also provides the structural richness to provide multi-element recommendations as learning paths.

Figure 1. Knowledge graph recommender system (KGRS) integration in the eDoer personalized learning Platform.

Construction of the eDoer’s Knowledge Graph

The construction of a knowledge graph is the process of defining its nodes and relations. Nodes in the knowledge graph represent the entities in the graph, and the relations show the semantic links between those entities.

We use a multidimensional knowledge graph in eDoer to model multiple types of entities and relations. This is meant to support the personalization and contextualization of the suggestion that the recommender system generates. The fundamental composition of the graph is equally informed and aligned to the pre-existing conceptual model of the taxonomic eDoer data structure.

Graph nodes

We define 6 types of graph nodes in eDoer:

- Jobs
- Skills
- Topics
- OER groups
- OERs
- Users

Each type of node is equipped with a set of properties, which include the metadata that is collected for the corresponding entity. For example, a job node has *industry* and *company* properties, while a skill node will have *assessment* and *learnable* properties, amongst others.

Graph relations

In order to represent the semantic relations between the different node types, we define multiple relation types between the graph nodes. Those relations link nodes of the same type, and nodes from multiple types as well. Those relations represent the links between:

Creating the relations in eDoer’s knowledge graph is meant to support the learning recommendations. Therefore, relation types were chosen and implemented to reflect the factors that influence this recommendation. Hierarchical graph relations were used to represent the links that experts defined when inserting new skills and OERs in the platform. Relation between nodes of the same type were introduced on several levels, to automatically create links between relevant nodes. User relations are generated to the corresponding nodes in the knowledge graph, based on their profiles, learning preferences, and learning goals. Figure 2 illustrates the first version of the eDoer knowledge graph, with its node types and relations. To discover and complete relations between related nodes an automatic relation prediction is used.

Automatic relation prediction is based on the similarity scores calculated between graph nodes. Node similarity results from:

- Textual similarity scores calculated between the descriptive content of the nodes, e.g. Job description.
- Taxonomic similarities that are retrieved from standard taxonomies, such as Skill-Skill relations retrieved from ESCO¹.
- Explicit, expert-defined, relations that are received from the crowdsourcing features of the eDoer platform.

¹ European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (<https://ec.europa.eu/esco/portal/home>)

Knowledge Graph Development Pipeline on eDoer

In order to provide the eDoer platform with graph recommendation services, and harmonize them with the expert-rule-based recommendations, we design the IT solution to utilize a graph transformation component. See Figure 3 which links the eDoer database to static and dynamic graph data layers. Graph data layers are used to model permanent and temporary, on demand created data in the knowledge graph, taking their level of sustainability into account when generating the recommendation.

Information modeled in the knowledge graph is then supported by external sources, which provide: 1) additional data sources, such as OER repositories, and 2) uniform structures, such as the ESCO taxonomy or EduCOR² ontology, which supports the generic nature of relations in the knowledge graph, and thus the graph's adaptability to new content.

Graph services are provided to eDoer platform, including:

- recommendations of skills, topics and OERs.
- retrieval of search results from the graph database.
- generations of learning paths from the graph structure.
- statistical information, calculated from graph metrics, such as centrality measures.

Figure 3. Structure of the IT solution concept for integrating graph services into the Doer learning platform..

² https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-88361-4_32

Development Infrastructure

We use the neo4j³ platform to develop and query the knowledge graph in eDoer. The neo4j environment provides the support for a large-scale knowledge graph modeling and utilization, with solid processing capabilities for graph focused processes, such as graph construction, curation and querying.

The eDoer knowledge graph is constructed based on the schema defined above. It provides the needed information for the recommender system, which is then queried from the eDoer platform through an API.

The API is designed to enable a two-way transfer of data and information, between the relational and graphical databases, see Figure1. Data and information transfer takes place through services, which each side of the API provides to the other. Services provided by the graphical database side include the search and retrieval, recommendations and statistical information. Services provided by the relational databases side include periodic data export and updates.

Development Time-plan

The development of the knowledge graph based recommender system is designed for a duration of 2 years, between May 2021 and May 2023. The development plan encompasses the following steps:

1. Development of the IT solution concept.
2. Implementation of the IT solution structure.
3. Defining the knowledge graph schema (graph node and relation definitions).
4. Construction of the eDoer knowledge graph in neo4j environment (the hierarchical relations)
5. Extension of the knowledge graph with a horizontal relation strategy.
6. Implementation of the graph API.
7. Generating graph search strategies and recommendations on the skill and topic level.
8. Creating a synchronization strategy and service between relational and graphical databases.
9. Extension of graph services to: contextual recommendation, learning paths.
10. Graph relation evaluation concept.
11. Graph content extension from online resources.
12. Graph uniformity and transformation functions.

Steps 1-5 have been accomplished in 2021. API construction is a current step taking place at the time of preparing this report. Steps 7-9 are planned for till September 2022. Steps 10-12 are planned for the last phase of the OSCAR project in August 2023.

³ <https://neo4j.com/>